
INNOVATIVE ICT ENABLED LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract:

Innovation means to discover new things, processes, to implement ideas. It is the need of the hour. Innovation has been main point of several organizations and institutions. Every organization Institution has to re-energize its policies, strategies by adopting & implementing innovative thoughts and ideas. The Information Technology revolution has brought about impact upon the society and economy activities. Information has become a significant component of world economy activity and being recognised as a major economic resource, organizations have grown to view their information resources as a strategic asset utilizing these resources as an instrument in enhancing the country's competitiveness in industry and international trade. Traditionally major organizational assets were classified human financial material, equipment and management resources view that during the decade of the 1980s. The technological advancement of information technology caused many organizations to regard their Information Technology resources as the sixth major organizational assets.

Keywords: *ICT, New Technology, Library Services, Digital Era*

Electronic Resources:

E-resources are those resources which need computer access or any sort of electronic products their deliver a collection of data. It may be text referring to full text based electronic journals image collections, other multimedia products or numerical, graphical or time bound. These may be delivered on CD-ROM on tape, via internet and so on. A number of techniques and related standards have been deployed which allow documents to be created and distributed in electronic form by over past year. In order to fulfill the users' demand and provide better facilities the library shifting towards new machines called Electronic Resources.

Day by day there is a development in new technologies. Internet also develops

continuously. These new technologies create new information in every field. It helps people to communicate with each other on the internet for example Blogs, wikis and social networks etc. This new environment gives rise to new opportunities for Information Professionals and extensively changes the librarians' work. The word academic is associated with learning, study, education or teaching. Academic libraries include school, college and universities libraries. They are often used teachers and students as a quiet place for study and research. The library collection includes print and non print material generally related to the syllabus of the students in their field of learning.

Computerized Library Services:

- To satisfy the user's needs & demands
- To save the time of the users
- To avoid the repetitive routine tasks
- To provide fast & accurate information to the users. To improve the efficiency internal operations & reducing the cost
- To educate & train both staff and users for computerized environment with the help of the technology.

The New Vision in the Libraries:

- If the future libraries are to survive they have to be switched over to electronic mode because the information is fast changing and mostly resources are bore digitally. At the same time digitization of libraries is not an easy task. It requires large amount of funds and skilled man power including the staff with a positive attitude, rich experience and expertise.
- The library is a member of the national digital library consortium and through it the global digital library is worked.
- The print material will be available in multimedia form.
- All services are accessible from home, work place and public libraries
- Information access/study time per student is 70% electronic print and 30% print.
- Library space 70% networked study space and 30% book stock.

The mission is to create a universal library which will foster creativity and free access to all human knowledge. As a first step in realizing this mission, it is proposed to create the universal library with a free to read, searchable collection of one million books, primarily in the English language available to everyone over the internet.

New Technology Development:

New technologies have always been of interest for libraries, both for the potential for increasing the quality of services and for improving efficiency of operations. RFID is an identification technology; it does the same job as barcodes but offers potentially a lot more. It can therefore be fruitful to look back at barcode technology and see what we can learn from its application in library operations. In applications at the circulation desk barcode technology has been proven to be robust, reliable, and efficient. In the effort to extend barcode technology to self service stations which is one major direction for achieving better efficiency in operations, the experience have been less than satisfactory. The cost for the self service stations should also be mentioned. The stations consist basically of the following components, a Windows PC, a metal cabinet (a fixed position), bar code reader, and special software. It also has the capability to deactivate the anti-theft device provide the item (volume) is put in the correct position.

Role of ICT in Library and Information Science:

Academic and research libraries are now being challenged by the rapidly growing new information and communication technologies (ICTs) like Internet, WWW, content Management systems and other virtual computer technologies. The goal of this paper is to provide the basic and the necessary information user expectation regarding the current trends and techniques in the ICT and knowledge management, which demands information handling, and provision of information services to the users. It also provides details about the computer networks, multimedia and

internet which play a vital role as the backbone of the information super highway in the field of ICT. The role of present day Librarians as ambassadors, the new trends and techniques of informatics, library networking systems, the importance of e-mail and internet facilities are also discussed. The digital library networks, its sources and the e-information services are described in a nutshell format. The virtual librarian to alter his role as a digital information manger and the total quality management systems to develop the libraries and the quality of the services are also provides. I hope that this paper addresses more current topic in ICTs by which the level of access and strategies to find right and relevant information have got the new facet and covers them in sufficient depth for the academicians and the library professionals to learn more about the modern role of ICTs in library and information science.

Library Services:

The range offered by automated library systems can be placed into three broad groups-

*** User Services:**

1. **OPAC Service:**-These are designed with a focus on the services to customers and offering real benefits to them. Eg. LYBSYS OPAC, SOUL OPAC,SOFTGRANTH OPAC,ETC.
2. **Web Opac Service:**- Web-OPACs are new generation of OPACs.Web-enabled OPACs allow user to search library catalogs and access other services from any client at anywhere at anytime.Eg.KOHA,Web-OPAC.
3. **Article Indexing Service:**-Modern automation packages also provide facility to create and index database of articles or papers published in the journals subscribed by the library.

4. **Lending Service:**-Lending Service provides facility to allow books and other library materials to be read elsewhere by users.

5. **Information Service:**-Display of general facts and figures about the library, library roles, contact persons for specific services, library map, library calendar and holidays, etc., CAS,SDI.

6. **Union Catalogue and ILL Service:**- Union catalogue is a collection of bibliographical details of resources belongs to a group of libraries. No library of this world is self-sufficient. Union catalogue helps user of one library to check the availability of required documents in other libraries, if not available in the stock of local library. Inter library loan (ILL) service handles the processing related with borrowing of items from collections beyond that of the local library.

7. **User support service:**-User support services help these users to know how to make the most effective and efficient use of an automated system. User support service includes: User orientation programme and library tour: Multimedia presentation and brief user manual; Customisable online tutorial that provides.

8. Electronic Document Delivery Service:-

These mechanisms have been made more efficient through the introduction of electronic document delivery.

*** MIS support services:**

Library management software deals with and contains huge amount of data related to documents, staff and users. The important resource and statistics are:

- a) Reports of items requested by users and supplied by vendors/ publishers;

- b) Reports on order status, overdue items, vendor performance, budget analysis etc.;
- c) Statistics related to exchange rate and price changes, average item cost etc.;
- d) Reports on items used, returned and reserved over a period and transaction history of members;
- e) Reports and statistics on most frequently issued items and most frequently visited members and
- f) Report on title history for journals and journal usage by members.

Impact of ICT on Library Services:

Library services are highly influenced due to impact of ICT adequate, Accurate and more efficient senders can be provided due to implementation of ICT. In addition to daily housekeeping operations the following services can be provided more efficiently due to ICT.

1. Current Awareness Services:

This service is rather more important to research scholar than the academic student. To keep the user more up to date with the progress within his/her subject is nothing but the current awareness service. It works in three steps first of all reviewing the information needed to the user secondly, selection of information from the various available and related, resources. Thirdly, recording the items to be brought to the attention of the user. This can be easily done with the help of ICT.

2. Selective Dissemination of information (SDI) Service:

This is another service which is important for the research and scholars, scientist. This is a type of CAS service provided to research scholar at regular intervals a list of carefully selected

publications in their areas of interest with the help of ICT.

Library and Mobile Technology:

Mobile devices create privacy concerns that do not arise in the physical environment of the library because there are limits to the tracking of physical content. In the past, patrons had to travel to their local library to access the card catalogue, check out books and other materials, ask questions of librarians, and participate in job workshops or library events. Although they had to take the time to get to the library building, they could use the library services with a reasonable amount of anonymity. Libraries have developed strong privacy protections for their users, especially in relation to borrowing records. When users check out physical media such as books, magazines or multimedia materials, they can be assured that the library will not reveal their circulation records or other personal information without a court warrant. Furthermore, the nature of material-the physical book, magazine volume, or DVD-prevents the library or other entities from gleaning much additional information about how the material was being used. Information technology, by contrast, offers the nearly limitless ability to capture granular information on both users and uses of content, with important consequences for freedom of inquiry.

Mobile technology and Library services:

Following are possible ways to send SMS from libraries, [Kumar & Chitra, 2008]

SMS alert services:

- Few Library automation software provide option to send SMS alerts for reserved items, due items to users. For example, Libsys0.7

- Plug-ins integrated with library email system to enable email to SMS messaging.
- Outsourcing the contract to a vendor to send alert services.

SMS alert service:

- Libraries might use SMS services in the following domains (M-Libraries, 2012).
- To send SMS to collect the requested books.
- Reminding the user if, book is due in his/her account; informing user about the exact fine.
- OPAC service.
- Users may request the opening and closing hours of the library.

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